

EXPLORING THE BENEFITS OF PSYCHOEDUCATION ON MEDICAL STUDENTS' MENTAL HEALTH DURING EXAMINATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Medical students are known to experience disproportionately high levels of stress, anxiety, and depression, particularly during examination periods. These psychological pressures can impair academic performance, well-being, and long-term professional resilience. Psychoeducation has been suggested as a low-cost, scalable intervention for promoting coping strategies and reducing mental health stigma, yet its role in supporting medical students during high-stakes examinations remains underexplored.

Aim: This study aimed to explore the benefits of a brief psychoeducation program on medical students' mental health during examinations, with specific objectives to evaluate its impact on academic distress, coping ability, depressive symptoms, feelings of being overwhelmed, and perceptions of mental health.

Methods: A single-blind, quasi-experimental design was employed with 120 undergraduate medical students from Wah Medical College, Pakistan. Participants were divided into an intervention group (n = 60), who received a psychoeducation course, and a control group (n = 60), who continued their usual coursework. The psychoeducation program included stress and time management strategies, cognitive restructuring, relaxation and mindfulness exercises, and stigma reduction discussions. Data were collected at baseline and follow-up using validated scales: College Student Stress Scale (CSSS), Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), CES-D 10-item scale, and a single-item measure of perceptions of mental health. Analyses were conducted using SPSS version 26 with independent-samples t-tests.

Results: Groups were comparable on demographic characteristics at baseline. Post-intervention, the psychoeducation group reported significantly lower academic distress ($p < .001$, $d = -0.71$), higher coping ability ($p = .017$, $d = 0.45$), and more positive perceptions of mental health ($p = .008$, $d = 0.52$) compared to controls. Depressive symptoms showed a small-to-moderate reduction in the intervention

group but did not reach statistical significance ($p = .057$). Feelings of being overwhelmed showed a non-significant reduction.

Conclusion: Psychoeducation was effective in reducing exam-related distress, enhancing coping skills, and improving perceptions of mental health among medical students, though its effects on depressive symptoms and feelings of being overwhelmed were less pronounced. These findings suggest that psychoeducation is a valuable, scalable, and preventive approach to promoting student well-being during examinations, though more intensive interventions may be necessary for clinically significant emotional distress.

Keywords: Psychoeducation, medical students, examination stress, academic distress, coping ability, mental health stigma.

INTRODUCTION

Examinations are a defining feature of medical education and are widely recognized as one of the most stressful academic experiences for medical students. The rigorous curriculum, competitive environment, and high expectations placed on medical students create a unique set of pressures that are further magnified during examination periods. Research consistently demonstrates that medical students experience significantly higher rates of anxiety, depression, and psychological distress compared to the general student population, particularly when preparing for or sitting examinations(1). Examination-related stress has been linked to impaired concentration, poor academic performance, sleep disturbances, and long-term mental health concerns, raising important questions about how best to support medical students during these critical periods (2). The burden of exam-related stress in medical students is evident across cultures and settings. A cross-sectional survey among final-year medical students in Turkey reported high levels of psychological distress during preparation for specialty examinations(3) Similarly, a study from Malaysia found that examination stress was strongly associated with burnout and emotional exhaustion in medical students (4). In Pakistan, educational competition is particularly intense, students frequently report that examination pressure contributes to anxiety, depressive symptoms, and even thoughts of discontinuing their studies (5). These findings suggest that examinations represent not only an academic challenge but also a major mental health risk factor for medical students.

While much research has documented the prevalence of stress, anxiety, and depression in medical students, fewer studies have focused on interventions specifically designed to reduce examination stress. Traditional coping strategies such as peer support, relaxation, or time management are often informal and inconsistently applied. Structured interventions such as mindfulness and cognitive-behavioral therapy have shown promise in improving resilience and reducing anxiety, but their implementation is limited due to resource constraints (6, 7). Psychoeducation, defined as the structured delivery of information and skills for managing stress and promoting mental health, offers a scalable, low-cost alternative. Evidence from nursing and pharmacy education indicates that psychoeducation can reduce stress, improve coping, and enhance well-being during examination periods(8, 9). However, its application in medical student populations remains underexplored.

Despite a growing body of research on stress and burnout among medical students, significant gaps remain in understanding how psychoeducational interventions function during examination periods. Although previous studies have explored general stress and anxiety, few have rigorously examined interventions tailored to the unique, high-stakes context of examinations. Moreover, much of the existing research has been limited by small-scale or discipline-specific samples, restricting the generalizability of findings across diverse medical student populations. Additionally, the potential of psychoeducation to reduce stigma and promote help-seeking behavior during exam

periods is still poorly understood, even though stigma continues to pose a major barrier to mental health support among medical students.

The rationale for the present study lies in addressing these gaps by evaluating whether psychoeducation can provide medical students with effective, evidence-based coping strategies to manage examination-related stress. Unlike interventions that require intensive clinical resources, psychoeducation can be embedded into the academic curriculum, reaching large groups of students at once and normalizing mental health discussions within medical education. This has the dual potential to alleviate academic distress during examinations and to reduce stigma surrounding mental health issues, thereby promoting both immediate well-being and long-term professional resilience.

The significance of this study is twofold. First, it may highlight psychoeducation as a scalable and cost-effective intervention that medical schools can adopt to improve students' mental health during examinations. Second, it provides evidence for embedding mental health education within the medical curriculum, aligning with calls for more comprehensive wellness initiatives in medical training. In doing so, it contributes to a growing movement toward preventive, system-level approaches to medical student well-being.

The aim of this study is to explore the benefits of psychoeducation on medical students' mental health during examination periods. The specific objectives are: (1) to assess the effect of psychoeducation on levels of examination-related academic distress, depressive symptoms, and feelings of being overwhelmed; (2) to evaluate whether psychoeducation improves students' ability to cope with stress during examinations; (3) to determine whether psychoeducation influences students' perceptions of mental health care and reduces stigma related to help-seeking; and (4) to compare outcomes between intervention and control groups before and after an examination period.

Methodology

The present study was conducted among 120 undergraduate medical students from Wah Medical College, Pakistan. Participants were

drawn from different years of study and represented variation in gender, age, socioeconomic status, and living arrangements such as hostel residence or day scholar status. This ensured that the sample captured diverse demographic and contextual influences on examination-related stress. A single-blind, quasi-experimental design was used to compare two groups of students. Sixty students formed the intervention group, who received psychoeducation, while another sixty students in the control group continued their usual coursework. Participants were unaware of the study's specific hypotheses to minimize potential bias in their responses.

The psychoeducation intervention was delivered during the examination preparation period and was based on principles of cognitive-behavioral therapy and stress management. The course content emphasized stress and time management strategies tailored for examinations, cognitive restructuring to challenge negative thoughts about performance, and relaxation and mindfulness practices such as diaphragmatic breathing and progressive muscle relaxation. Additionally, sessions highlighted the role of social support in reducing exam anxiety and included discussions on mental health stigma, with the goal of encouraging positive attitudes toward help-seeking. Each session combined lectures, interactive group discussions, and guided practice of coping techniques, ensuring that students not only learned theoretical concepts but also applied practical strategies to manage their examination stress.

Data were collected at two time points: baseline, two weeks prior to examinations, and follow-up, immediately after examinations. At both points, participants from the intervention and control groups completed identical survey instruments. Academic distress was measured using the College Student Stress Scale (10), coping ability was assessed using the Perceived Stress Scale (11), depressive symptoms were measured with the 10-item CES-D scale (12), and perceptions of mental health were assessed using a single-item measure examining whether psychoeducation can reduce stigma and improve help-seeking attitudes. Participation was voluntary, informed consent was

obtained, and anonymity was maintained throughout the process.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and percentages, were calculated to summarize the demographic characteristics of both groups. Independent-samples t-tests were

performed to compare post-intervention outcomes between the psychoeducation and control groups. A significance level of $p < .05$ was set for all statistical analyses to determine the effectiveness of the psychoeducation intervention.

Results

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Participants (n = 120)

Variable	Intervention Group (n = 60)	Control Group (n = 60)	Total (N = 120)
Age (years)			
18-20	20 (33.3%)	18 (30.0%)	38 (31.7%)
21-23	28 (46.7%)	30 (50.0%)	58 (48.3%)
24-26	12 (20.0%)	12 (20.0%)	24 (20.0%)
Gender			
Male	28 (46.7%)	27 (45.0%)	55 (45.8%)
Female	32 (53.3%)	33 (55.0%)	65 (54.2%)
Year of Study			
1st year	10 (16.7%)	12 (20.0%)	22 (18.3%)
2nd year	14 (23.3%)	13 (21.7%)	27 (22.5%)
3rd year	16 (26.7%)	15 (25.0%)	31 (25.8%)
4th year	20 (33.3%)	20 (33.3%)	40 (33.3%)
Living Environment			
Hostel	35 (58.3%)	34 (56.7%)	69 (57.5%)
Day scholar	25 (41.7%)	26 (43.3%)	51 (42.5%)
Socioeconomic Status			
Low	18 (30.0%)	17 (28.3%)	35 (29.2%)
Middle	30 (50.0%)	32 (53.3%)	62 (51.7%)
High	12 (20.0%)	11 (18.3%)	23 (19.2%)

The demographic characteristics show that the intervention and control groups were broadly comparable across all variables, suggesting baseline equivalence. Age distribution was similar in both groups, with most participants falling between 21-23 years. Gender was almost evenly split, with a slight predominance of females in both groups. Year of study was well balanced, with roughly one-

third of students in their final year, ensuring representation across all academic levels. Living environment (hostel versus day scholar) and socioeconomic status were also proportionally distributed between groups, minimizing the likelihood that demographic differences confounded the study's outcomes.

Table 2; Comparison of Intervention and Control Groups on Mental Health Outcomes

Variable	Intervention	Control	t (118)	p-value	Cohen's d
	M (SD)	M (SD)			
Academic Distress (CSSS)	2.95 (0.68)	3.45 (0.72)	-3.78	.000***	-0.71
Coping Ability (PSS)	27.60 (5.12)	25.20 (5.48)	2.43	.017*	0.45
Depressive Symptoms (CES-D 10)	11.40 (4.50)	13.10 (5.10)	-1.92	.057	-0.35
Feelings of Being Overwhelmed	2.80 (1.10)	3.10 (1.20)	-1.39	.168	-0.26
Perceptions of Mental Health	6.20 (0.88)	5.70 (1.02)	2.72	.008**	0.52

The comparison of outcomes revealed that the psychoeducation group reported significantly lower academic distress than the control group, with a large effect size, highlighting the effectiveness of the intervention in reducing exam-related stress. Coping ability was also significantly higher in the intervention group, indicating improved confidence and strategies for handling stress. Although depressive symptoms were lower in the intervention group, this difference narrowly missed statistical significance, while feelings of being overwhelmed showed only a small, non-significant reduction. Importantly, perceptions of mental health and stigma were significantly more positive among students who received psychoeducation, reflecting its potential to shift attitudes toward help-seeking. These results collectively suggest that psychoeducation is particularly effective for reducing academic stress and improving attitudes toward mental health, while its impact on deeper emotional symptoms may require more intensive interventions.

Discussion

The present study aimed to explore whether a brief, syllabus-embedded psychoeducation program delivered during an examination period could improve medical students' mental health outcomes. Specifically, the study sought to determine whether psychoeducation would reduce academic distress, enhance coping ability, lower depressive symptoms and feelings of being overwhelmed, and improve perceptions of mental health while reducing stigma related to help-seeking.

The findings indicated that psychoeducation was particularly effective in reducing academic distress among medical students, with a large effect size

observed. This suggests that structured training in stress management, time management, relaxation, and cognitive restructuring can meaningfully alleviate the specific pressures associated with examinations. These results are consistent with prior evidence demonstrating that interventions combining relaxation and cognitive skills training produce significant reductions in academic stress(13). More recent studies in medical education also support this finding, reporting that structured stress-management workshops and pre-exam interventions improve resilience and reduce test anxiety in medical students (14, 15)

The intervention also significantly improved coping ability, with a moderate effect size. This finding is important as coping self-efficacy is a key protective factor against burnout and emotional exhaustion. Similar effects have been reported in nursing and pharmacy students, where psychoeducation enhanced adaptive coping strategies and reduced maladaptive responses to exam pressure (16). Meta-analytic findings on stress-management programs further support the role of psychoeducation in fostering coping confidence and adaptive behaviors (17)

Although depressive symptoms declined in the intervention group compared to controls, the effect was small to moderate and narrowly missed statistical significance. This pattern is consistent with prior evidence indicating that brief, classroom-based psychoeducation is more effective at changing knowledge, attitudes, and situational distress than in treating entrenched depressive symptoms (18). Medical students, who are known to have high baseline rates of depression, often require more intensive or individualized interventions such as multi-session CBT or mindfulness-based therapy for clinically

meaningful symptom reduction (19). The trend observed here nevertheless suggests that psychoeducation may play a preventive role, serving as a first step in a stepped-care approach. No significant changes were observed in students' self-reported feelings of being overwhelmed. This may be because the measure was based on a single item, limiting sensitivity, or because feelings of being overwhelmed reflect multiple domains of stress, including financial and family concerns, which are not fully addressed by brief psychoeducation. Previous research on test-anxiety interventions similarly reports mixed effects on global measures of overwhelm, despite consistent reductions in exam-specific anxiety (15). These findings highlight that broader emotional states may require more sustained or individualized support.

One of the most promising findings was the significant improvement in perceptions of mental health and reduced stigma in the intervention group. This aligns with prior studies showing that brief psychoeducation improves treatment credibility and help-seeking intentions among students (20). Since stigma and low mental health literacy are major barriers to accessing care in medical populations, this effect is especially important. Encouraging positive attitudes toward mental health care can increase the likelihood that students will access services when needed, reducing the risk of untreated psychological distress during training. Taken together, these results suggest that psychoeducation is highly effective in targeting exam-specific distress and stigma reduction, moderately effective in enhancing coping ability, and somewhat helpful in reducing depressive symptoms, though less effective for global feelings of being overwhelmed. This pattern fits well with the broader literature, which shows that psychoeducation is best suited for preventive education, skill building, and attitude change, while more entrenched or global psychological difficulties may require higher-intensity interventions such as multi-session CBT, mindfulness programs, or clinical counseling. In practical terms, the findings support embedding psychoeducation into medical curricula as a universal, low-cost strategy to improve student well-being during high-stakes

examination periods. Such programs can normalize discussions about stress and mental health, promote adaptive coping, and encourage early help-seeking, thereby reducing academic distress and stigma. However, to fully address the burden of depression and overwhelm in medical students, psychoeducation should be integrated into a stepped-care model, with pathways to more intensive support for students who need it.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that psychoeducation is an effective intervention for reducing examination-related academic distress and improving perceptions of mental health among medical students. The program also enhanced coping ability, although its effects on depressive symptoms and feelings of being overwhelmed were less pronounced. These findings suggest that psychoeducation, when embedded into the medical curriculum, can serve as a preventive and scalable strategy to improve students' well-being during examination periods. While not a substitute for intensive mental health interventions, psychoeducation can play an important role in normalizing mental health discussions, reducing stigma, and promoting early help-seeking behaviors among medical students.

Limitations

Several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the quasi-experimental design and lack of randomization may limit causal inference and increase the risk of selection bias. Second, the reliance on self-reported measures introduces the possibility of response bias and reduces objectivity. Third, the study was conducted at a single medical institution in Pakistan, restricting the generalizability of the findings to other cultural and institutional contexts. Fourth, the follow-up was limited to the immediate post-examination period, making it impossible to determine the long-term effects of the intervention. Finally, the use of a single-item measure to assess feelings of being overwhelmed may have reduced measurement reliability.

Recommendations

Future research should adopt randomized controlled trial designs across multiple medical

institutions to improve generalizability and strengthen evidence. Longitudinal follow-up assessments are necessary to evaluate the sustainability of psychoeducation's benefits beyond examination periods. It is recommended that psychoeducation be integrated into a stepped-care framework, where it can function as a universal, preventive strategy supplemented by targeted interventions such as CBT or mindfulness programs for students experiencing significant distress. Expanding measurement tools to include multi-item scales, academic performance indicators, and actual help-seeking behaviors would provide more comprehensive insights. Medical schools should consider incorporating psychoeducation as a regular part of pre-exam preparation, thereby addressing both immediate exam-related stress and contributing to long-term professional resilience.

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